

A Quantum-Safe Authentication Scheme for IoT Devices using Homomorphic Encryption and Weak Physical Unclonable Functions with no Helper Data

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Abstract. Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) are widely used to authenticate electronic devices because they take advantage of random variations in the manufacturing process that are unique to each device and cannot be cloned. Therefore, each device can be uniquely identified and counterfeit devices can be detected. Weak PUFs, which support a relatively small number of challenge-response pairs (CRPs), are simple and easy to construct. Device authentication with weak PUFs typically uses helper data to obfuscate and recover a cryptographic key that is then required by a cryptographic authentication scheme. However, these schemes are vulnerable to helper-data attacks and many of them do not protect conveniently the PUF responses, which are sensitive data, as well as are not resistant to attacks performed by quantum computers. This paper proposes an authentication scheme that avoids the aforementioned weaknesses by not using helper data, protecting the PUF response with a quantum-safe homomorphic encryption, and by using a two-server setup. Specifically, the CRYSTALS-KYBER public key cryptographic algorithm is used for its quantum resistance and suitability for resource-constrained Internet-of-Things (IoT) devices. The practicality of the proposal was tested on an ESP32 microcontroller using its internal SRAM as a SRAM PUF. For PUF responses of 512 bits, the encryption execution time ranges from 16.41 ms to 41.08 ms, depending on the desired level of security. In terms of memory, the device only needs to store between 800 and 1,568 bytes. This makes the solution post-quantum secure, lightweight and affordable for IoT devices with limited computing, memory, and power resources.

Keywords: PUFs; post-quantum security; Kyber; homomorphic encryption; device authentication; privacy techniques

1. Introduction

Nowadays, the interconnection of different types of Internet-of-Things (IoT) devices has led to a variety of new applications in vital areas such as healthcare, transportation or industry. In a typical IoT application, sensors and actuators are used to collect data, process them to derive useful information and take some action based on them [1]. As these devices are remotely managed, their authentication is critical to ensure the trustworthiness of the application and avoid potential damage. Counterfeit devices are a major concern in applications that require high levels of security. Due to the constrained nature of many IoT devices (they have low computing, memory, and power resources), authentication solutions should be affordable in terms of execution time, bandwidth, size of the information to be stored in the devices, and energy consumption.

An emerging way to authenticate IoT nodes is through the use of Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) [2]. A silicon PUF in the hardware of an IoT device is able to map the random variations in the manufacturing process of the device chip into a unique device identifier [3]. A PUF can be thought of as a black box with a challenge as an input and a response as an output, where the Challenge-Response Pairs (CRPs) are all the available inputs and outputs that can be managed by the PUF. Since the process variations in the semiconductor manufacturing are unpredictable and cannot be controlled, it is not possible to produce two PUFs with the same CRPs. In addition, PUFs are tamper-resistant because if they are modified, their responses to the challenges are also modified. Therefore, PUF-based identifiers are well suited for the detection of counterfeit devices.

The number of CRPs determines whether a PUF is weak or strong. Weak PUFs can support a relatively small number of CRPs while strong PUFs can support a much larger number. Strong PUFs have been widely used in authentication solutions that do not require complex post-processing or cryptographic constructions. However, the problem with strong PUFs is that several research results have demonstrated that they can be modeled and attacked by machine learning techniques [4]. Thus, despite the use of strong PUFs in the devices, several impersonation attacks reported in the literature show that an attacker is successful when using an impostor instead of a genuine device [5]. Therefore, this paper focuses on the use of weak PUFs.

Many weak PUFs are easy to construct and therefore inexpensive. For example, a Static Random-Access Memory (SRAM) PUF can be constructed simply by using the start-up values of the SRAM cells as the

responses. Unlike authentication with strong PUFs, weak PUFs require the use of complementary constructions. Among them, a dominant construction is the so-called code-offset-based fuzzy extractor [6]. It consists of the following two phases. In the enrollment phase, a PUF response is used to obfuscate a cryptographic key and generate non-sensitive auxiliary data called helper data. Instead of storing the cryptographic key, which is sensitive, the helper data are stored. In the key reconstruction phase, a fresh PUF response is used in conjunction with the helper data to recover the cryptographic key. The helper data, which are typically stored in the device, are used with an error correction code because the PUF is not completely reliable and the response has errors that should be corrected to properly recover the cryptographic key.

A problem with the use of weak PUFs and helper data for device authentication are the helper-data manipulation attacks. Hence, in several scenarios, an attacker can be assumed to actively manipulate the helper data to weaken the security of the authentication scheme. To avoid these attacks, robust fuzzy extractors have been proposed [7]. However, the problem of building efficient and robust fuzzy extractors for PUFs remains an open problem, as Becker argues in [8]. Besides helper-data manipulation attacks, there are works in the literature that report other ways to attack helper data [9]. One way to avoid these attacks is to directly eliminate the use of helper data. This has been proposed in [10][11] by improving the reliability of weak PUFs. However, this approach is very expensive because requires changes in the manufacturing phase. In our work, we propose an inexpensive scheme that can be used with any weak PUF without the use of helper data. Thus, we avoid all kinds of attacks that target the helper data.

Regarding the cryptographic algorithms used in conjunction with PUFs, they should be chosen carefully due to the imminent arrival of quantum computers. Typically, classical cryptographic algorithms such as the Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA), which will be completely broken by quantum computers, are used in IoT devices [12]. Therefore, quantum-safe algorithms should be considered for implementation in IoT devices if long-term solutions are required. Among them, hash-based signatures, such as XMSS (eXtended Merkle Signature Scheme) and LMS (Leighton-Micali Scheme), have been proposed. The NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology of USA) has published a recommendation for their use in [13]. The combination of SRAM PUFs with the XMSS scheme is proposed in [14]. NIST also started a process to standardize selected quantum-safe algorithms [15]. Some proposals have already been selected for standardization [16], such as CRYSTALS-KYBER for public-key encryption and key establishment (referred to herein as Kyber) and CRYSTALS-DILITHIUM for digital signatures (referred to herein as Dilithium). CRYSTALS algorithms are based on the Module Learning With Errors (M-LWE) problem (a variant of the Learning With Errors (LWE) lattice problem). Kyber encryption has an interesting homomorphic property that has been proposed in [17] for a biometric template protection scheme. There are also works in the literature that focus on the combination of PUFs with non-standard LWE cryptographic systems [18]. In this work, a scheme is proposed whose security relies on Kyber, which at the time of writing, is the only quantum-resistant public-key encryption and key establishment algorithm proposed for standardization by NIST [16].

The contributions of this paper are the following:

- A quantum-safe authentication scheme suitable for constrained IoT devices is presented based on homomorphic encryption with Kyber and PUFs. As reported in literature, Kyber is well suited to constrained devices due to its low execution times and low energy consumption in comparison with other quantum-resistant schemes [19][20][21], which is very convenient for homomorphic encryption solutions. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first quantum-safe authentication scheme using homomorphic encryption with Kyber and PUFs.
- The proposed authentication scheme is a low-cost solution since it can be used with any type of weak PUF, regardless of its reliability and number of CRPs, and does not need any helper data. Note that the security of helper data remains an open problem in the literature [8]. The approach taken in this paper is inexpensive, unlike other solutions in the literature that avoid the use of helper data [10][11]. Thus, we fill the gap in the literature on PUF authentication without the need for helper data and without an expensive solution.
- The proposed scheme offers a high security. In the one side, it uses a two-server setup, where two servers instead of only one have to be attacked to obtain the PUF responses, which is sensitive information about the device. In the other side, PUF responses are always protected and are never processed in plaintext by the servers thanks to the use of homomorphic encryption based on Kyber.

- The suitability of the proposal for constrained devices has been validated experimentally with IoT devices using the SRAM PUFs of their ESP32 microcontrollers.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 summarizes the state of the art related to the proposal. Section 3 presents some preliminaries about PUFs and Kyber encryption. The proposed solution of the paper is shown in Section 4. Section 5 discusses the carried experimental results. Conclusions are given in Section 6.

2. Related Work

As briefly introduced above, helper data are auxiliary data that are widely used in fuzzy extractors to compensate for the unavoidable unreliability of PUF responses due to noise. They are used as non-sensitive data that allow to recover sensitive data such as a cryptographic key. However, despite the widespread use of the fuzzy extractors, helper-data manipulation attacks pose a threat to these schemes that use weak PUFs [22-28].

The helper-data manipulation attack presented in [22] allows learning information about the PUF response. The work in [23] shows how the manipulation of the helper data can lead to a partial or complete leakage of the supposedly secret cryptographic key in some constructions with ring-oscillator PUFs. [24] shows that the alternative to the fuzzy extractor presented in [25] is also vulnerable. Furthermore, the manipulation of the helper data is an enabler for the fault attack presented in [26]. More recent solutions, such as the Two-Metric Helper Data construction [27], have been shown to be highly vulnerable to side-channel attacks [28], especially when the helper data are public, as usual.

In [8], Boyen et al. present a construction that is provably secure against helper-data manipulation attack and allows reusing challenge-response pairs, which is called robust and reusable fuzzy extractor. However, Becker's work in [9] shows that it is not feasible to build a robust fuzzy extractor that satisfies the security proof of Boyen et al. and at the same time achieves the error correction rates required by usual PUFs in the key reconstruction phases of fuzzy extractors. Becker's work also emphasizes that a well-formed reconstruction phase should not only check that the key reconstructed is valid, but it must also check that the Hamming distance between the PUF responses used at enrollment and reconstruction phases is smaller than the correcting upper bound of the error correction code. Becker presents a number of helper data manipulation attacks that exploit the absence of checking of this distance. The efficient construction of robust and reusable fuzzy extractors is a current research line [29].

There are works in the literature that focus on proposing PUF constructions that are reliable enough to not require error correction and, hence, helper data. In [11], a construction called Locally Enhanced Defectivity PUF (LEDPUF) is shown to be highly reliable. Reliability is achieved by locally manipulating physical layout designs to deliberately introduce permanent defects as stable sources of local randomness. A more recent proposal is shown in [12], where a highly stable PUF is obtained by using two random gate oxide breakdown mechanisms, plasma-induced and voltage-stressed breakdowns. This proposal also requires some intervention in the fabrication process. This makes these solutions complex and expensive to implement.

Regarding authentication protocols that avoid the use of helper data, a recent work can be found in [30], where the authors present an authentication and key agreement protocol that uses PUFs in conjunction with an error correction scheme. In an enrollment phase, the authentication server requests a set of CRPs from the PUF and builds a model from them. Later, in the authentication phase, the PUF model is used to authenticate the true PUF. The problem is that PUF responses are sensitive since they are intrinsically linked to the device and cannot be revoked. Hence, if a server knows the CRPs in cleartext, it knows a very relevant feature of the device that cannot be changed, like a biometric feature in a human. Also, if the server is attacked, the PUF model can be used to impersonate the device.

Concerning quantum-safe authentication schemes, the work in [31] presents a scheme that uses the LWE (Learning With Error)-based computational fuzzy extractor proposed in [32] by Fuller et al. Since the LWE problem is used to generate the helper data, they are resistant to attacks from quantum computers. The authentication scheme needs a secure enrollment phase in which an issuer collects a set of CRPs from the PUF and stores them in a database accessible for the authentication server. The problem, again, is that those

Table 1

Comparison between the solution proposed in this paper and works found in literature.

Problem	This work	[11]	[12]	[14]	[30]	[31]	[33]	[34]	[35]
Quantum computers attacks	No	*	*	No	No	No	No	No	No
Helper data attacks	No	*	*	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Expensive solution	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No	No
Non-protected PUF responses	No	*	*	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No

* Depends on the used protocol.

CRPs are sensitive data about the device and a data breach or any interception of those data during the authentication process can break the security of the scheme.

Following with quantum-safe authentication schemes, the work in [33] uses Learning Parity with Noise (LPN) commitments in a zero-knowledge protocol. The LPN problem is the simplest version of the LWE problem. The work in [14] combines the use of the eXtended Merkle Signature Scheme for device authentication with the use of a SRAM PUF for secret key reconstruction. The XMSS scheme was one of the first signatures to be specified in RFC8391, and its interest led NIST to publish a recommendation in [13]. In [34], mutual authentication between an IoT device and an authentication server can be achieved by using the Kyber algorithm to secure the communication channel. A novel type of device identification based on the behavioral and physical characteristics of an SRAM, collected by BPUFs (Behavioral PUFs), is employed to allow a multi-modal authentication of the device [35]. In all these proposals, weak PUFs with helper data are used in some step of the authentication scheme and, hence, they are vulnerable to helper-data attacks.

Table 1 summarizes how the proposed solution focuses on avoiding the above-commented problems found in the related work available in the literature.

3. Preliminaries

In order to understand how weak PUFs can be used in an authentication scheme without helper data, this section includes a first subsection that summarizes the basic principles of PUFs. To understand how quantum-safe homomorphic encryption can be used in an authentication scheme with PUFs, the second subsection is dedicated to the Kyber public-key encryption algorithm.

3.1. Authentication of IoT devices using PUFs

Authentication is the procedure in which a party proves its identity to another one. In the case of devices, authenticity is usually proven with the use of a binary string that should be used only by that device. Many times, this binary string is a private key used by the device in a cryptographic authentication protocol. The private key is something the device knows or has (it is stored in its memory) but it is not linked to the physical identity of the device. As human biometrics authenticate people by who each individual is, Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs) allow authenticating devices by which each electronic device is. The variability of the manufacturing process of electronic devices are captured by PUFs as the genetic variability of people is captured by biometrics.

There are a large variety of PUFs, including but not limited to PUFs based on delays, memories, acoustics, optics and magnets. PUFs based on memories and, in particular, PUFs based on SRAMs are very extended since they are embedded in many IoT devices so that no additional hardware is required. SRAMs are composed of array structures of memory cells. Each SRAM cell is a bistable circuit with two cross-coupled inverters. A write operation forces the SRAM cell to transition towards one of the two stable states but if the cell is powered-up and no write operation is carried out, the positive feedback between the two inverters leads the cell to the start-up value imposed by the inverter which begins to conduct. There are

intrinsic conditions, related to mismatching between the inverters due to the variability of semiconductor fabrication process, that make one inverter be the winner. Hence, the start-up values of SRAMs are taken as the responses of SRAM PUFs.

There are certain metrics that are commonly used in the literature [36]. Since PUF responses are usually binary strings, their difference is measured with the Hamming distance. The Hamming Distance (HD) between two responses, r_i and r_j , with n bits ($r_i, r_j \in \{0,1\}^n$) is computed as follows:

$$HD(r_i, r_j) = \sum_{b=0}^{n-1} (r_i[b] \oplus r_j[b]) \quad (1)$$

where $r_i[b]$ represents the b -th bit of the response r_i . The Fractional Hamming Distance (FHD) is calculated as HD/n .

The difference between PUF responses is modeled as a binary symmetric channel assuming that all bits are independent. This was demonstrated experimentally in [37] for the case of SRAM PUFs. Given an experiment E , the probability distribution used to model the appearance of exactly t different bits in the PUF responses is a binomial distribution, as follows:

$$P(E = t) = \binom{n}{t} p^t \cdot (1 - p)^{n-t} \quad (2)$$

where p is the probability of a different bit, which is the same for a 0 that changes to 1 and for a 1 that changes to 0 (because it is assumed a symmetric model).

Hamming distances between responses of the same PUF instance to the same challenges (genuine population) are called intra Hamming distances. If a PUF is perfectly reliable, intra Hamming distances are always zero. However, if reliability (or reproducibility) is not perfect, as usual, there are always some response bits that change from one measurement r_i to another r_j (known as flipping bits), which generates noise. For a given response r , the average intra FHD , \overline{FHD}_{intra} , measures unreliability as follows:

$$\overline{FHD}_{intra}(r) = \frac{2}{K(K-1)} \sum_{i=0}^{K-2} \sum_{j=i+1}^{K-1} \frac{HD(r_i, r_j)}{n} \quad (3)$$

\overline{FHD}_{intra} is normalized by the number of FHD s that can be calculated using K responses r , which is $K \cdot (K - 1)/2$.

Hamming distances evaluated between responses of different PUF instances to the same challenges (impostor population) are called inter Hamming distances. For a given response r , the average inter FHD , \overline{FHD}_{inter} , of PUFs in L devices is computed as follows:

$$\overline{FHD}_{inter}(r) = \frac{2}{L(L-1)} \sum_{i=0}^{L-2} \sum_{j=i+1}^{L-1} \frac{HD(r_i, r_j)}{n} \quad (4)$$

\overline{FHD}_{inter} is normalized by the number of FHD s that can be calculated using the response r provided by L devices. If the number of 1's and 0's in the PUF responses are the same (unbiased responses) and their position is perfectly random, which happens in unpredictable and unique responses, the average inter FHD is 0.5.

Using (2), the probability that a genuine response of n bits contains more than HD_{max} errors is given by:

$$P_G(E > HD_{max}) = 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{HD_{max}} \binom{n}{i} p_G^i \cdot (1 - p_G)^{n-i} \quad (5)$$

The probability of a different bit in the genuine responses, p_G , can be estimated experimentally as the \overline{FHD}_{intra} in (3).

Also using (2), the probability that an impostor response of n bits contains less than HD_{max} different bits is given by:

$$P_I(E < HD_{max}) = \sum_{i=0}^{HD_{max}-1} \binom{n}{i} p_I^i \cdot (1 - p_I)^{n-i} \quad (6)$$

Table 2
Steps of Kyber algorithm.

Kyber.CPAPKE.KeyGen()	Kyber.CPAPKE.Enc($PK = (t, \rho), m \in \mathcal{M}$)	Kyber.CPAPKE.Dec($SK = s, C = (u, v)$)
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. $\rho, \sigma \leftarrow \{0,1\}^n$ 2. $\mathbf{A} \sim R_q^{k \times k} := \text{Sam}(\rho)$ 3. $(\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{e}) \sim \beta_\eta^k \times \beta_\eta^k := \text{Sam}(\sigma)$ 4. $\mathbf{t} := \text{Compress}_q(\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{s} + \mathbf{e}, d_t)$ 5. return $PK := (t, \rho), SK := s$ 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. $r \leftarrow \{0,1\}^n$ 2. $\mathbf{t} := \text{Decompress}_q(t, d_t)$ 3. $\mathbf{A} \sim R_q^{k \times k} := \text{Sam}(\rho)$ 4. $(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{e}_2) \sim \beta_\eta^k \times \beta_\eta^k \times \beta_\eta := \text{Sam}(r)$ 5. $\mathbf{u} := \text{Compress}_q(\mathbf{A}^T \cdot \mathbf{r} + \mathbf{e}_1, d_u)$ 6. $v := \text{Compress}_q(\mathbf{t}^T \cdot \mathbf{r} + \mathbf{e}_2 + [q/2] \cdot m, d_v)$ 7. return $C := (u, v)$ 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. $\mathbf{u} := \text{Decompress}_q(u, d_u)$ 2. $v := \text{Decompress}_q(v, d_v)$ 3. $m' := \text{Compress}_q(v - \mathbf{s}^T \cdot \mathbf{u}, 1)$ 4. return m'

The probability of a different bit in the impostor responses, p_I , can be estimated experimentally as the FHD_{inter} in (4).

As will be explained in Section 4 and analyzed in Section 5, the proposal in this work uses the responses of SRAM PUFs, a threshold HD_{max} and the probabilities in (5) and (6) to evaluate if a device is authentic or not. No other auxiliary data are required.

3.2. Public-Key Encryption using Kyber

In order to achieve long-term security, cryptographic solutions should be resistant to quantum computers. The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) initiated at the end of 2016 a process to standardize quantum-resistant cryptographic solutions. In July 2022, the third round was completed and Kyber public-key encryption and key-establishment solution was selected for its standardization [16]. Kyber is based on lattice cryptography and, concretely, the Module-Learning-With-Errors (M-LWE) problem. The development and security analysis of Kyber public-key encryption can be found in [38].

Kyber is defined by key generation, encryption, and decryption algorithms. Its basic steps are shown in Table 2. The key-generation algorithm returns a pair (PK, SK) consisting of a public key and a secret key, respectively. The encryption algorithm takes a public key PK and a message $m \in \mathcal{M}$ (with $\mathcal{M} \subseteq \{0,1\}^n$) to produce a ciphertext c . Finally, the decryption algorithm takes a secret key SK and a ciphertext c , and outputs either a message $m \in \mathcal{M}$ or a special symbol \perp to indicate rejection.

Let \mathbb{Z}_q denote the ring of integers modulo an integer q , and R and R_q denote the rings $\mathbb{Z}[X]/(X^n + 1)$ and $\mathbb{Z}_q[X]/(X^n + 1)$, respectively, where $n = 2^{n'} - 1$ such that $X^n + 1$ is the $2^{n'}$ -th cyclotomic polynomial. The notation employed is that regular font letters denote elements in R or R_q (which includes elements in \mathbb{Z} and \mathbb{Z}_q), bold lower-case letters represent vectors with coefficients in R or R_q , and bold upper-case letters are matrices. For a vector \mathbf{t} (or matrix \mathbf{A}), we denote by \mathbf{t}^T (or \mathbf{A}^T) its transpose. β_η is a centered binomial distribution with parameter η , where η is even, and the samples are in the interval $[-\eta/2, \eta/2)$. Sam is an extendable output function XOF (its output can be extended to any desired length). $y \sim S := \text{Sam}(x)$ means that Sam takes as input x and produces a value y that is distributed according to distribution S . If the distribution is uniform for a value r , then the notation is $r \leftarrow \{0,1\}^n$. The operator $[x]$ denotes rounding to the x nearest integer. $\text{Compress}_q(x, d)$ takes an input $x \in R_q$ and outputs an integer in $\{0, \dots, 2^d - 1\}$, where $d < \lceil \log_2(q) \rceil$; if $x \in R_q^k$, the procedure is applied to each coefficient individually. $\text{Decompress}_q(x, d)$ takes an input $x \in \mathbb{Z}_q$ and outputs $[(q/2^d) \cdot x]$; if $x \in R_q^k$, the procedure is applied to each coefficient individually. $\text{Compress}_q(v - \mathbf{s}^T \cdot \mathbf{u}, 1)$ outputs 1 if $v - \mathbf{s}^T \cdot \mathbf{u}$ is closer to $[q/2]$, and 0 otherwise.

An interesting feature of Kyber encryption algorithm is that if a same message is encrypted several times, the obtained ciphertexts are different because randomness is added every time.

4. Proposal of Authentication Scheme

This section contains five subsections to explain: first, the overview of the proposed scheme together with the assumptions; second, the homomorphic encryption applied with Kyber; and finally, the detailed phases of the scheme.

4.1. Overview and Assumptions

Three main parties are involved in the authentication scheme: 1) the device DEV, which is the entity that is authenticated each time the protocol is executed, 2) the database server DBS, which stores a protected version of the PUF response of the device DEV, and 3) the authentication server AS, which is the entity that ultimately verifies the authenticity of the IoT device DEV. In addition, there is a manufacturer MAN that performs the characterization of the devices to conveniently select the threshold HD_{max} to evaluate whether a device is authentic or not. Since the device DEV can be authenticated to many database servers, DBSs, the MAN and the DBSs come to an agreement and the former provides the latter with the thresholds required for the device authentication process.

We aim to propose an authentication scheme using PUFs that can be used with any type of weak PUF, regardless of its reliability and number of challenge-response pairs (CRPs). We also want the scheme to be resistant to helper data attacks and, hence, a scheme that does not require any type of helper data is pursued. Since a PUF response is very sensitive information from the device, we pay attention to how this response is stored outside the device itself. Finally, we want to propose a solution with long-term security and, hence, a quantum-resistant solution is pursued.

In the following, we present the assumptions about the device DEV, the database server DBS and the authentication server AS, as well as the assumptions about the allowed attacks.

We assume that the DEV has a PUF with at least one CRP. Thus, the proposal is suitable for any PUF, regardless of the number of CRPs available. It is also assumed that the device DEV has a True Random Number Generator (TRNG) capable of generating the true random numbers required by the encryption process. An attacker can have access to the non-volatile memory of the device DEV, since it is not protected. The PUF responses read by the DEV should not be accessible to an attacker.

The database server DBS and the authentication server AS cannot collude, i.e. they will not exchange information that could compromise the privacy of the device DEV. They also behave honestly. However, they may be curious and want to learn as much information as possible about the IoT device. This is a typical assumption in biometric template protection schemes using homomorphic encryption [17], which can be extrapolated to this solution using PUFs. It is assumed that the servers cannot be directly compromised by an attacker as they are not resource constrained and can be better protected.

Regarding the communication channels, it is assumed that DBS and AS communicate via a secure and authenticated channel, i.e. the communication is encrypted and some cryptographic primitive is used to verify each other's identity. It is also assumed that the communication channel between the device DEV and the database server DBS is also secure and that DEV can verify the identity of DBS. Note that the literature shows that this is affordable for IoT devices using protocols such as KEMTLS [19][20][21][39]. Our proposal addresses the challenge of device authentication without storing permanently a secret key at the device. Finally, we assume fresh communication so that replay attacks are not allowed. This can be achieved by employing protocols that use ephemeral keys such as KEMTLS [19] or nonces.

The Kyber public-key encryption and decryption algorithms (Kyber.CPAPKE.Enc() and Kyber.CPAPKE.Dec(), respectively, part of the Cryptographic Suite for Algebraic Lattices (CRYSTALS) package submitted to the NIST post-quantum cryptography standardization process and selected for standardization [38] are chosen to protect the PUF responses of the device DEV.

4.2. Homomorphic Encryption with Kyber

The *Kyber.CPAPKE.Enc* algorithm with public key PK encrypts binary messages of length n (n of 256 bits (32 bytes) was used in the experimental results in Section 5). If the PUF response r (i.e. the message to be encrypted) is of length p (with $p > n$), the data must be divided into r^i blocks with $i = 1, \dots, \lceil p/n \rceil$. If n does not divide p or $p < n$, a padding must be appended to the data. The protected PUF response R can then be represented as follows:

$$R = \text{Kyber.CPAPKE.Enc}(r, PK) = \{\text{Kyber.CPAPKE.Enc}(r^i, PK) \mid 1 \leq i \leq \lceil p/n \rceil\} \quad (7)$$

The comparison in the protected domain is based on the fact that Kyber public key encryption algorithms fulfil the following homomorphic property:

$$\text{Poly.Sub}(R_1, R_2) = \text{Kyber.CPAPKE.Enc}(r_1^i, PK) - \text{Kyber.CPAPKE.Enc}(r_2^i, PK) =$$

$$= (\mathbf{u}_1^i - \mathbf{u}_2^i, v_1^i - v_2^i) = \text{Kyber.CPAPKE.Enc}(r_1^i \text{ XOR } r_2^i, PK) \quad (8)$$

where r_1 and r_2 are PUF responses, ‘-’ is the coefficient-wise subtraction operation applied to each polynomial that conforms the ciphertexts, the XOR operation is applied to the binary PUF responses, and $\mathbf{u}_1^i, \mathbf{u}_2^i, v_1^i$ and v_2^i are the vectors of polynomials and polynomials described in Subsection 3.2. Then the Hamming distance of r_1 and r_2 in the protected domain can be calculated as follows:

$$HD(\mathbf{r}_1, \mathbf{r}_2) = \sum_{i=1}^{\lceil p/n \rceil} HW(\text{Kyber.CPAPKE.Dec}\left(\begin{matrix} \text{Kyber.CPAPKE.Enc}(PK, r_1^i) \\ \text{Kyber.CPAPKE.Enc}(PK, r_2^i) \end{matrix}, SK\right)) \quad (9)$$

where SK is the private key and $HW(\mathbf{x})$ is the Hamming weight (the number of 1’s) of the vector \mathbf{x} .

4.3. Setup Phase

In the setup phase, the database server DBS sends the threshold value HD_{max} found in the device characterization process to the authentication server AS. The AS then generates the pair of secret and public keys (SK, PK) using the key generation algorithm $\text{Kyber.CPAPKE.KeyGen}$ specified in [40]. The public key PK is transferred to the database server DBS for a later use in the enrollment and authentication phases. The authentication server AS stores the secret key SK and HD_{max} in a secure manner. These steps are illustrated in Figure 1.

We assume that the setup phase takes place in a protected environment where the servers cannot be attacked. The protected environment could be a place where strict protocols are followed to ensure the trustworthiness of the processes. This is what happens in real applications. Exact protocols to ensure the controlled environment are beyond the scope of this work. Attacks on manufacturing facilities and countermeasures are a studied topic in the literature and they can be applied to create the controlled environment [41][42][43].

4.4. Enrollment Phase

In this phase, the database server DBS initializes the interaction by sending a challenge c to the device DEV, together with the public key PK and the unique ID for device identification. Later, the device generates a new PUF response r_0 corresponding with the challenge c . The response r_0 is encrypted using the public key encryption algorithm Kyber.CPAPKE.Enc from [40], resulting in the protected PUF response R_0 . This operation requires the use of the TRNG built into the device, as the encryption process internally uses a random string of 32 bytes [40]. The protected response R_0 is sent to the database server DBS, which stores R_0 together with the device identifier ID and the challenge c . These steps are shown in Figure 1.

Like the setup phase, the enrollment phase takes place in a controlled and protected environment to avoid any leakage of sensitive device authentication information. Note that authentication and database servers are not resource constrained. Therefore, they can be well protected by additional mechanisms such

Fig. 1: Setup and enrollment phases.

Fig. 2: Authentication phase.

as Trusted Platform Modules (TPMs) and Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs). Additional protocols should be used to ensure that the device has not been tampered with in the facilities where the enrollment phase takes place. If this is not achieved, an attacker could have access to the PUF response and impersonate the device.

4.5. Authentication Phase

In the authentication phase, shown in Figure 2, the device DEV sends its identifier ID to the database server DBS, which responds with the challenge c used in the enrollment phase. The device then uses its PUF to generate a new response r_i . Later, the device encrypts the response using the public key PK and the algorithm *Kyber.CPAPKE.Enc* as was done in the enrollment phase. The protected fresh response R_i is sent to the database server DBS.

Once the encrypted fresh physical response R_i is received, the database server DBS computes the difference between R_i and the protected reference response R_0 stored in the enrollment phase. This is done for each block contained in the protected responses. The database server DBS then forwards the protected difference D_i to the authentication server AS.

Finally, the authentication server AS decrypts D_i using its secret key SK and the *Kyber.CPAPKE.Dec* of [40], and obtains the difference in plaintext d_i . By calculating the Hamming weight of d_i , the authentication server AS knows the Hamming distance HD_i between the fresh response and the reference one, i.e., the number of errors that the fresh response has with respect to the reference one. The Hamming distance HD_i is then compared with the threshold HD_{max} to determine whether the device is authentic or not.

DBS and AS communicate via a secure and authenticated channel, i.e. the communication is encrypted and some cryptographic primitive is used to verify each other's identity. The communication channel between the device DEV and the database server DBS is also secure and DEV knows the identity of DBS.

5. Experimental results and discussion

5.1. Experimental Setup

The proposal was evaluated using a Pycom WiPy 3.0 board, which includes an Espressif ESP32 microcontroller. ESP32 microcontrollers are widely used in IoT applications due to their low cost and wireless connectivity, as they have Bluetooth and WiFi modules. The board has 8 MB of external flash memory. The ESP32 microcontroller is based on a Xtensa dual-core LX6 processor and has 512 kB of internal SRAM. A clock frequency of 160 MHz was selected for the experiments. The microcontroller has

an internal hardware true random number generator based on the thermal noise of the system and the asynchronous clock mismatch. This module is used to generate the randomness required for cryptographic operations. We use the ESP32 internal SRAM as the SRAM PUF. To characterize the SRAM PUF, we used 25,593 bytes with addresses ranging from 0x3FFD9C00 to 0x3FFDFFF9. The number of boards used to characterize the SRAM PUF was 7 and we took 2,000 measurements from each board with a 5-second delay between measurements. We used the ESP32 deep sleep mode and serial communication with a PC at a default baud rate of 115,200. The reference implementation of the Kyber Key Encapsulation Mechanism (KEM) was used to perform the Kyber encryption operation. Specifically, the `incdpa_enc` function implemented in the `incdpa.c` file was considered.

5.2. PUF Characterization

For characterizing the SRAM PUF, we analyzed the genuine and impostor populations by calculating the intra and inter fractional hamming distances, respectively, between the measured responses. For the genuine population, the distances were computed between responses of the same board, using the first 200 measurements of the total. For the impostor population, the distances were computed between responses from different boards. The resulting histograms are shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that the two populations are clearly distinguishable and form two separate sets. The average of the inter fractional hamming distances (of the impostor population) is 0.4843 and the average of the intra fractional hamming distances (of the genuine population) is 0.0537. These values correspond with the average inter-chip and intra-chip fractional hamming distances typically found in PUF characterization [36] and explained in Section 3.1. The fractional hamming distance between the maximum of the genuine population and the minimum of the impostor population is of 0.2656, which shows that there is a security margin in the authentication.

Since the bit differences in an SRAM PUF response can be modeled as a random variable that behaves like a binary symmetric channel (as was explained in Subsection 3.1), Equation (5) can be applied to find the threshold distance HD_{max} that produces a false rejection rate, $P_G(E > HD_{max})$, of 10^{-6} , taking as the bit error probability, p_G , the average intra fractional hamming distance mentioned above. A false rejection rate of 10^{-6} is considered low enough to properly authenticate a genuine device. The threshold value HD_{max} , which depends on the size of the PUF response, is shown in Table 3 for sizes of 256, 512, 768 and 1,024 bits.

Substituting the threshold values HD_{max} given in Table 3 into Equation (6) and taking as the bit error probability, p_I , the average inter fractional hamming distance mentioned above, the false acceptance rate,

Fig. 3: Histograms of the intra-chip (on the left) and inter-chip (on the right) fractional hamming distances (FHD).

Table 3
Threshold values HD_{max} and probability of attack with false acceptance for several SRAM PUF response sizes.

PUF size (bits)	HD_{max}	Probability of attack	Bit security
256	35	$5.0956 \cdot 10^{-32}$	103
512	56	$6.0126 \cdot 10^{-74}$	243
768	76	$2.6770 \cdot 10^{-117}$	387
1024	95	$8.5979 \cdot 10^{-162}$	535

$P_I(E < HD_{max})$, can be calculated. This is the probability that the authentication server will accept an impostor device used by an attacker as genuine. These attack probabilities are shown in the third column of Table 3. The corresponding bit securities are shown in the fourth column. The probabilities of attack shown in Table 3 are higher than the probabilities of applying a brute force attack because in the latter case, the attacker would apply a bit error probability, p_I , of 0.5 instead of the value 0.4843 that an attacker applies if uses an impostor device. Therefore, the bit securities shown are the worst cases. Note that as the size of the SRAM PUF response increases, so does the bit security, making the calculation of the probability of attack for different sizes a potential method for selecting the size in bits of the responses. Based on the experimental results, a size of 512 bits with a bit security of 243 bits may be sufficient for the SRAM PUF of the internal memory of the ESP32. Larger responses may be considered for a more robust security and the 256-bit size may only be selected in more restrictive applications.

5.3. Performance of the Proposal

The performance of the proposal was evaluated from the point of view of the IoT device, in terms of the execution time of the cryptographic operations that the device should perform, the communication bandwidth required to send the authentication data, and the non-volatile memory required. The proposal is compared with other quantum-safe device authentication solutions based on SRAM PUFs, digital signature algorithms and fuzzy extractors. The quantum-safe digital signature algorithms considered were Dilithium (based on lattices) and SPHINCS+ (based on hashes), which were selected for standardization in the NIST Post-Quantum Cryptography Standardization Process [16]. Falcon was not considered because it is not suitable for embedded devices without floating-point arithmetic units. A 16-bit error correction code was chosen for the fuzzy extractor to reconstruct the secret key employed in the digital signature algorithm.

As with many cryptographic protocols, the execution of cryptographic operations is the most time consuming. These times were evaluated for different PUF response sizes and different security levels. The results are shown in Figure 4. The execution times of the Kyber encryption operation are very low, which confirms that this algorithm is very well suited for IoT devices, as mentioned in other works in the literature [19]-[21]. For the lowest security level of 128 bits, which could be chosen if the most lightweight application of the proposal is required, the execution times range from about 8 ms to 33 ms depending on the size of the PUF responses, being of 16 ms for the recommended size of 512 bits. For the medium security level of 192 bits, the execution times range from about 14 ms to 54 ms, being of 27 ms for the 512-bit size. This is the security level that could be chosen for most applications, as it offers the best trade-off between security and performance. For example, the security of 192 bits is the lowest allowed by NIST Special Publication 800-208, which is intended for stateful hash-based signatures [13]. For a more conservative security level of 256 bits, the execution times range from about 21 ms to 82 ms, with 54 ms for the 512-bit size. Thus, if the security level needs to be updated over time, this will not result in a large change in execution time. Figure 4 also shows the results using the combination of a fuzzy extractor and a

Fig. 4: Execution times (for different security levels) of the proposal with Kyber (This work) and a solution based on signatures with Dilithium.

digital signature algorithm based on Dilithium, which belongs to the same cryptographic suite as Kyber. Although Dilithium also uses lattices in its construction, the proposed solution provides better execution times at all security levels. Specifically, it is 4.9 times faster than the Dilithium solution for a 192-bit security level and considering a 512-bit PUF response. SPHINCS+ provided very slow execution times (4.5 s for a 128-bit security level, 16 s for a 192-bit security level and 35 s for a 256-bit security level). Since their signing times are about three orders of magnitude higher than the other solutions, they are not shown in Figure 4.

The communication bandwidth of the proposal is shown in Figure 5. It was analyzed in terms of size of the encrypted PUF response, since the Kyber encryption algorithm increases from 24 to 49 times the size of the protected PUF response and this affects the amount of data to be sent. Note that this bandwidth increases if a security layer such as TLS is added to the proposal, but we do not consider this for clarity. The bandwidth ranges from 768 to 3,072 bytes for a 128-bit security level, from 1,088 to 4,352 bytes for a 192-bit security level and from 1,568 to 6,272 bytes for a 256-bit security level. For 512-bit PUF responses, it ranges from 1,536 to 3,072 bytes. Compared to solutions based on fuzzy extractors and quantum-safe digital signatures, the results are similar to Dilithium-based solutions and lower than SPHINCS+-based

Fig. 5: Required bandwidth (for different security levels) of the proposal with Kyber (This work) and solutions based on signatures with Dilithium and SPHINCS+.

Fig. 6: Required storage in the device (for different security levels) of the proposal with Kyber (This work) and solutions based on signatures with Dilithium and SPHINCS+.

solutions. Specifically, at 512 bits, the Kyber encryption has a bandwidth 1.5 times smaller than the Dilithium signature, and at 768 bits, both solutions have similar bandwidths. The bandwidth with SPHINCS+ is about an order of magnitude larger than the others. In any case, the bandwidth is always on the order of kilobytes, which may or may not be significant depending on the application, but is affordable in most cases.

The non-volatile memory requirements of the device are shown in Figure 6. They consist of the storage of the public key used for the Kyber CPA encryption algorithm. The results obtained were 800 bytes for a 128-bit security level, 1,184 bytes for a 192-bit security level and 1,568 bytes for a 256-bit security level. These numbers are not a problem for the Wipy 3.0 board used, as it has 8 MB of external flash memory storage. Even more constrained microcontrollers, such as the LPC11U68 [44], can afford to store the public key. Note that there is no need to store any helper data. The proposal with Kyber encryption is the one with the least requirements. The helper data needed to reconstruct the secret key for signing with Dilithium are 54.2 times larger than the public key needed by Kyber to encrypt a 512-bit physical response for a 192-bit security level, so the difference is really significant. While it is true that the Wipy board can in principle handle the size of the helper data mentioned, this may be an issue for more constrained embedded platforms, or it may have an impact on the main application of the device. Signing with SPHINCS+ requires smaller helper data, only 1.3 times larger than the Kyber public key in the same comparison.

In our proposal, the most demanding operation on the IoT device side is the encryption of the PUF response with the Kyber encryption algorithm. In [21], the power/energy consumption of the Kyber encapsulation algorithm considering different security levels are reported and compared with other schemes such as the Elliptic-Curve Diffie-Hellman (ECDH) or the Elliptic-Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA), which are widely used in embedded devices today (a Nucleo-F439Zi board equipped with a 32-bit ARM Cortex-M4 is used as embedded device). Note that the encapsulation operation is dominated by the encryption operation [40]. These results, shown in Table 4, depict that even the Kyber1024 encapsulation instance consumes less than the ECDSA signature commonly used in embedded devices. Hence, we argue that our proposal is suitable for an embedded device from a power/energy consumption point of view.

In summary, when considering a post-quantum solution, our proposal is lighter on the device side due to shorter execution times and less non-volatile memory requirements. Also, the proposal has low energy consumption. Another advantage is that in our solution, no sensitive information vulnerable to attack is stored in the device. The entity that stores the secret key is the authentication server, which clearly has many resources to protect it.

Table 4

Results of power/energy consumption of various cryptographic algorithms reported in [21].

Scheme	Power (mW)	Energy (mJ)
ECDHE Enc. (secp256r)	190.000	3.369
ECDSA Sign. (secp256r)	185.500	2.283
RSA 2048-bit Sign.	139.700	62.621
Kyber512 Enc.	156.100	0.974
Kyber768 Enc.	157.900	1.802
Kyber1024 Enc.	160.400	1.864

6. Conclusions

This paper proposes a novel approach for device authentication using PUFs together with a PUF response protection scheme based on homomorphic encryption and a two-server setting. In the enrollment phase, a database server stores a reference encrypted PUF response. Then, in the authentication phase, the device sends a fresh encrypted PUF response to the database server. The database server computes the difference between the reference and fresh encrypted PUF responses and sends the result to an authentication server. The authentication server decrypts the encrypted difference and compares it with a threshold to determine the authenticity of the device. Specifically, the proposal uses the Kyber public-key encryption algorithm, selected for standardization in the NIST post-quantum cryptography competition, and, hence, is ready for the quantum era. Kyber public-key encryption satisfies homomorphic properties and is very suitable for resource-constrained battery-powered IoT devices.

The solution is suitable for any weak PUF, since only one CRP is required. Also, it is resistant to helper-data attacks, since no helper data are needed to support the operation of the PUF. As the PUF response is never seen in plaintext at any step of the scheme and two servers need to be attacked instead of one, the security is high on the server side. As our solution does not require any changes to the PUF manufacturing process, it is not as expensive as other solutions in the literature.

The solution was evaluated in an ESP32 microcontroller, commonly used in IoT devices, using its internal SRAM as SRAM PUF. The experimental results showed that genuine and impostor populations of PUF responses can be distinguished properly using Hamming distances. The security of these SRAM PUFs was also evaluated based on the probability of a false-acceptance attack because the probabilities of that attack were higher than the probabilities of applying a brute force attack. The result is that the security levels ranged from 103 to 503 bits depending on the PUF response sizes. The performance results showed that the proposal is competitive with other authentication solutions in terms of execution times, communication bandwidth and non-volatile memory. The PUF response encryption operation took from 8.26 to 82.02 ms to execute, and the size of the encrypted PUF responses ranged from 768 to 6,272 bytes. The non-volatile memory required to store the scheme's public key in the device ranged from 800 to 1,568 bytes.

As future work, we plan to evaluate the proposed solution in other types of devices and platforms, primarily Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs). This will include using other types of PUFs, such as ring-oscillator-PUFs, and accelerating the Kyber encryption operation by hardware. The authentication scheme will also be extended and adapted to include a behavioural response by improving the work reported in [34]. To further evaluate the security of the proposal, we plan to test the scheme against side-channel attacks.

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